

Computation of Algebraic Equations of Combinatorial Geometric Series

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper presents a technique to find the solutions of algebraic equations taken away from the different combinatorics geometric series. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to compute the multiple summations of a geometric series [1-12], a new idea stimulated his mind to create a new type of geometric series. As a result, a combinatorial geometric series [12-20] was developed with new idea of binomial coefficients.

2. System of Binomial Coefficients

The combinatorial geometric series is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial geometric series [17-31] refers to the binomial coefficient [28-40].

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i,$$

$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ denotes the combinatorial geometric series and V_n^r the binomial coefficient.

$N = \{V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_5^1, \dots\} = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots\}$ is a set of natural numbers,

where $V_0^1 = 1; V_1^1 = 2; V_2^1 = 3; V_3^1 = 4; V_4^1 = 5; V_5^1 = 6; \dots$

Let us show that V_n^r belongs to the set of natural numbers, *i. e.* $V_n^r \in N$,

where, $V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!}$ and integers $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$.

$V_0^1 = 1; V_1^1 = 2; V_2^1 = 3; V_3^1 = 4; V_4^1 = 5; V_5^1 = 6; \dots$

Let $V_n^r = V_{Q-1}^1$, where $Q = V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!}$.

$$V_{Q-1}^1 = \frac{(Q-1+1)}{1!} = Q \quad (OR) \quad V_{V_n^r-1}^1 = \frac{(V_n^r-1+1)}{1!} = V_n^r.$$

$\therefore V_n^r$ belongs to the set of natural numbers, i. e. $V_n^r \in N$.

3. Polynomial Algebraic Expression

$R = \{x^i \mid -\infty < x^i < +\infty \text{ \& } i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ is a set of real numbers OR real line.

Let us take away some monomial algebraic expressions from the combinatorial geometric series such as $V_k^r x^k, V_{k+1}^r x^{k+1}, V_{k+1}^r x^{k+1}, \dots$, and $V_n^r x^k$.

If we assign a real number for $V_k^r x^k$, then we can find a real value for x^k , i. e. $V_k^r x^k = c$.

For example, $V_1^1 x^1 = 0.1 \Rightarrow 2x = 0.1 \Rightarrow x = 0.05$.

Combinatorial geometric series is a polynomial algebraic expression,

$$i. e. P(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i.$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i = 0 \text{ is a polynomial algebraic equation.}$$

Let us find the solutions for two algebraic equations shown below:

$$V_k^r x^k + V_{k+1}^r x^{k+1} = c_1 \text{ taken away from } \sum_{i=0}^p V_i^r x^i \text{ and}$$

$$V_k^n x^k + V_{k+1}^n x^{k+1} = c_2 \text{ from } \sum_{i=0}^q V_i^r x^i, \text{ where } c_1 \text{ and } c_2 \text{ are numerical constants.}$$

By solving the algebraic equations, we get the solutions for x^k and x^{k+1} .

$$i. e. x^k = \frac{V_{k+1}^r c_2 - V_{k+1}^n c_1}{V_k^n V_{k+1}^r - V_k^r V_{k+1}^n} \text{ and } x^{k+1} = \frac{V_k^r c_2 - V_k^n c_1}{V_k^r V_{k+1}^n - V_k^n V_{k+1}^r}.$$

4. Conclusion

This article provides the solutions for the algebraic equations taken away from the distinct combinatorial geometric series. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real world problems.

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